

Influence of Selected Government Regulations on Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects in Kenya: A Case of Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation, Nairobi County, Kenya

^{1*}Daniel Mutongi Amuyunzu, ² Johnbosco Mutuku Kisimbii

¹Master of Arts in Project Planning and Management Student, ²Lecturer

^{1,2}Department of Open Learning, University of Nairobi, Kenya

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of selected government regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation (REREC) in Nairobi county Kenya. The study adopted descriptive research design with a target population of 481 permanent employees of REREC, the study settled for a sample size of 140 respondents obtained using stratified random sampling method. Research questionnaires were administered to the employees at REREC headquarters within Nairobi. Descriptive statistics involved frequency distribution, percentages, mean and standard deviation. Inferential analysis involved OLS regression. The regression analysis revealed that financial regulations, construction standards and codes and competence of project team had a significant positive influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects whereas environmental regulations and county government licensing exhibited a negative influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The study therefore concluded that the selected government regulations considered under the study had a significant influence on implementation public infrastructure projects by REREC. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the management of REREC should ensure that they do not contravene any of the environmental regulation. Secondly, the study recommends that REREC must continue to invest in new construction technologies and observe standards recommended in the construction codes and standards books. Thirdly, the study suggests that the management of REREC must adhere to the Public Financial Management Act and the Public Procurement and Assets Disposal Act. The study also recommends that the county government should adopt standard licensing procedures. Finally, the study recommends that the management at REREC should continue recruiting highly qualified employees for its vacant positions.

Keywords: Government Regulations, project implementation, Infrastructure Project

I. INTRODUCTION

Globally, countries are focusing on public infrastructure projects in order to realize economic prosperity and improve the well-being of its population. Investment in public infrastructure has the potential to accelerate development within a country in a sustainable manner by employing contemporary techniques and methods of construction. The success realized in public infrastructure development to enhance economic transformation is best realized by interaction with experts in various fields of development. The critical position occupied by public infrastructure projects in economic transformation on development of countries is recognized in chapter 27 of Agenda 21 of UN" (UN charter 1945). Niazi and Painting (2017) noted that critical roles played by public infrastructure projects including enhancing literacy rates, eradication of poverty and opening up the remote areas of the country. The study further recommends that all development projects of infrastructure in nature must come to completion for them to be worthwhile in transforming the lives of the citizens. Hodge and Greve (2017) revealed that the chief financier of public infrastructure projects is the government who dedicates development expenditure to public infrastructure projects. Despite the critical function of public infrastructure projects in an economy, they have significant externalities for instance influence on the ecosystem (Cunningham, O'reilly, Dolan, O'kane& Mangematin, 2016). To start with, the production of cement, a key component in building construction, which is significant for every infrastructure project, emits greenhouse gases that deplete the ozone layer and the effect is global warming (Beckrich, 2018). Additionally, such projects lead to pollution of the

environment including air pollution, solid waste, noise pollution, and water pollution. Further, the construction of infrastructure projects uses a big chunk of a nation's development expenditure hence there is need for accountability through public financial regulations (Santin, Itard&Visscher, 2019). The regulatory controls put in place for infrastructural projects development is thus necessary and unavoidable. In response to the increasing environmental degradation and need for accountability, various countries around the world have developed legislations and policies to regulate construction activities and ensure that construction projects have minimum impact on the environment (Cunningham et al. 2016).

Globally, studies have examined the impact of regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects. In Singapore, Christudason (2018) indicates that the environmental issues and concerns have led to the development of environmental policies like EPCA. In the Europe, Parsa and Farshchi (2016) found that multilateral environmental legislations have been developed to regulate the construction industries so as to prevent and mitigate advanced negative impacts associated with environmental contamination. In china, Lu and Tam (2013) on waste management evaluated the effectiveness of construction waste management policies. The study revealed that waste management philosophies have reduced wastes drastically. In Ghana, Ametepey, Ansah and Edu-Buandoh (2015), asserts that the government has developed environmental regulations that include Environmental Assessment Regulations Act, Environmental Sanitation Policy and building code. In Ghana, Yalley et al. (2015) found that more than 50% of the construction firms in the building sector had never obtained an environmental permit. In Nigeria, Zarewa, Ibrahim, Ibrahim and Adogbo (2018) evaluated the relationship between implementation of large infrastructure projects and governance. The research revealed that governance adopted in projects affected the projects both negatively and positively (Zarewa, Ibrahim, Ibrahim &Adogbo, 2018). Locally in Kenya, Kenya public infrastructure report of 2018, reported that the domestic government is major financier of public infrastructure projects with the rest of the funding coming from non-government multinational entities such World Bank, African Development Bank, USAID and CIDA. Additionally, Gichamba and Kithinji, (2019) on the influence of environmental regulations on the Nairobi county construction projects revealed that waste management and water use regulations had a major impact on construction projects performance. Additionally, the study revealed that physical planning and noise regulations did not have significant effect on the performance of construction projects. Another study in Nairobi Kenya by Ndumia, (2015) evaluated the causal effect link between construction regulations and the performance of construction projects undertaken in Nairobi county Kenya. The study established that various regulations had significant effect on construction projects.

A public infrastructure project is said to be implemented when the beneficiaries are able to get public goods and services promised to them in the right quantity, at the right time and right quality. Apart from beneficiary satisfaction, a project is delivered when carried within the budgeted costs and time. Beneficiary satisfaction, cost and time are key measures for project delivery. The primary proxies of public infrastructure projects performance are cost and schedule of performance (Oguntona&Aigbavboa, 2019). The project performance in terms of cost and schedule are usually grouped under the economic measures of project performance. Developing countries are faced with the issue of limited financial resources when undertaking public infrastructure projects hence cost of the project is a critical factor in project evaluation. For a long time, successful implementation of a project has been defined based on minimization of completion time & management of budget constraints. However, contemporary Project Management practises are increasingly focusing on meeting business outcomes via multiple criteria (Erebor, Ibem&Adewale, 2019). Project completion and beneficiary satisfaction are critical success criteria for projects. The constraints of cost, time & scope determine the successful completion of a project. Consequently, beneficiary's satisfaction is derived from quality, utility and operation (Gichamba&Kithinji, 2019). Study by Ayebeeng and Yeboah-Boateng (2019) noted that institutions consider project implementation success to include meeting business aims such as on-time implementation of product, achieving contractual specifications and within specified budget figures. Study by Lamka, Masu, Wanyona, Dianga and Gwaya (2017) noted that project implementation sometimes depends on targets that have been set by clients within the three constraints of time, cost and scope. Project implementation is also conceptualised by the process of implementation as the value perceived in advance on what is to be delivered (Ametepey, Aigbavboa&Ansah, 2015). Government regulations are rules, principles and norms that guide economic activities whose enforcement is usually through fines and penalties when breached (Assbeihat, 2016). There are various government regulations affecting infrastructural project implementation including county government licensing, environment regulations, financial management regulations and construction standards and codes.

Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation (REREC) formerly REA was set under "Section 66 of the Energy Act, 2006 (No 12 of 2006)" as the Authority. The successor, REREC, came to be under "Section 43 of the Energy

Act of 2019.” The two names may be used interchangeably to refer to same institution under this current study. Further, at times two words Authority (which means REA) and the Corporation (which means REREC) may come into play to mean the same organization. The Authority is a creation of the act of parliament to fast track electrification and connections of electricity in the rural areas. The function was hived from the Ministry of Energy and the Kenya Power. The purpose of REREC was to ensure faster connection of electricity in the under developed parts of the country with the aim of enhancing socio economic development in such areas. REREC is charged with the role of connecting the rural areas with affordable and high quality power with the sole goal of transforming rural setting into economic hubs capable of achieving sustainable socio economic development (REREC, 2020). REREC achieves the function via two approaches including grid extension and autonomous diesel operated or solar operated generation plants. The grid extension ensures that the national grid is extended to the rural areas while diesel or solar system are used in areas that are off the national grid system (REREC, 2019). Currently, REREC is actively involved in developing and promoting photovoltaic solar solutions to be used in the rural areas. REREC is also seeking the public private partnership deals with private investors for the purpose of collaboration in generation and distribution of electricity in the rural homes. Given the dwindling supply of hydroelectric power, REREC has become a critical institution of harnessing the renewable energy for improving the livelihood of rural dwellers (Kraak, Ricker & Engelhardt, 2018). Inadequate access to affordable and high-quality energy is a hindrance to the vision of transforming the developing economies into middle-income status by supporting industrialization and enhancing the lives of the poor masses who often stay in the rural areas of various countries. Khatib, (2016). The provision of quality and affordable energy is one of the critical pathways to bridge the development gap between the first world countries and the third world developing nations.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Public Infrastructure project implementation is very critical to the development of any county; however, the implementation of the projects must be carried out within set government regulations. Government regulations are critical and must be observed during implementation of all infrastructural projects. Infrastructural projects therefore need to be carried within set government regulations (Marleno, Surjono, Wateno, Muhammad & Dahlan, 2018). Studies have been done globally and locally on the association between government regulations and project implementation. Jobidon, Lemieux and Beauregard (2018) revealed that transactional nature of procurement is important in the achievement of project delivery. Zarewa, Ibrahim and Adogbo (2018) revealed that success of infrastructure projects can be attributed to adequate funding of project throughout from the initiation to completion, proper initiation, well integrated risk management avenues, support from top strategic manager and efficient government policies and process. Gichamba and Kithinji (2019) revealed that waste management and water use regulations had a major impact on construction projects performance. Ogetii (2019) revealed that compliance level with the occupation health and safety standards was derailed by lack of advised knowledge on safety practices, exorbitant safety costs, negative impact on project schedule, lack of commitment by management and lower productivity. Mutheu and Muturi (2018) established that budgetary controls, access to funding and training on financial management significantly affected the performance of county government projects. Mbiti (2017) established that that project team competency, top management support, building information modelling technology and stakeholder participation had major impact on implementation effectiveness of SGR project. Even with studies already carried out, a few gaps still exist in the literature. First, most studies on Government regulations and infrastructural project implementation have concentrated on environmental and construction regulations with few studies examining financial management regulations. Secondly, majority of studies done locally have tended to focus on other kinds of projects with few studies focusing on pure public infrastructure projects. Thirdly, scanty literature exists on moderating influence of project team competence on the relationship between government regulations and public infrastructure project delivery. The study therefore sought to fill a gap in literature by examining the influence of government regulation on the implementation of public infrastructure projects at the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation in Nairobi County, Kenya.

1.2 Objectives of the study

The study sought to establish the influence of selected government regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation in Nairobi County Kenya. The study sought to examine the following specific objectives:

1. To establish the effect of environmental regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.
2. To analyze the effect of construction standards and codes on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

3. To establish the effect of public financial management regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.
4. To examine the effect of county government licensing on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.
5. To establish the moderating effect of competence of project team on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

1.3 Research Hypotheses

This study tested the following research hypotheses at the 95% level of significance:

H₀₁ Environmental regulations have no significant influence on the implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation

H₀₂ Construction standards and codes have no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

H₀₃ Public financial management regulations have no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

H₀₄ County government licensing has no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

H₀₅ Competence of project team does not moderate the relationship between selected government regulations and implementation of public infrastructure projects by the Rural Electrification and Renewable Energy Corporation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Public Interest Theory of regulation

Public Interest Theory of regulation was advanced by Becker (1986) to describe the regulations that seek to protect and benefit the public. In majority of the societies, there exists a basic assumption whereby people should carry on their businesses in their own interests (Mizutani, & Nakamura, 2019). As they carry their businesses, they meet other people who influence them, or they are influenced by their activities. When the government and other regulations are put in place to influence the business interests, citizens tend to benefit from their activities. Lindrianasari, Kufepaksi, Asmaranti, and Komalasari (2018) elucidated on the concept of the regulatory capture where the project implementers influence the regulators and the public interest is ignored at the altar of profitability. Public interest theory of regulation has been criticized for putting the public interest above that of project developers. The public interest goal if not balanced with the interest of the project developer may lead to developers running into losses that would in term affect the output of such projects (Johnston, 2017). Public Interest Theory of regulation is relevant in the current study on the relationship between selected government regulations and implementation of public infrastructure projects undertaken by REREC. The theory explains how government comes in to regulate the activities of private sectors for the benefit of the public. The interest of the public is critical before any project can be implemented. The regulation of public infrastructure projects is made in order to meet the public' demands and thus ensuring customer satisfaction.

2.1.2 Competency Theory

Competency theory was developed by McClelland & McBer in the 1980s. The scholars defined competency as the qualities in a person that are related to superior performance in a job environment. The competency are the skills, training and attitude possessed by employees to make them effective in the job environment by contributing effectively and efficiently to the achievement of the organizational goals (Elhami, Ban, Mousaviasl& Zahedi, 2018). The theory explains that the competencies possessed by project management staff is critical for the firms to develop systems, expertise and infrastructure to necessary to provide high quality products and services that satisfies consumers' needs beyond that of competing firms (Muraraneza&Mtshali, 2018). The theory further holds that the integration of a variety of production skills and technologies would enable and organizations to create value to its current and prospective customers by supplying quality products and services. The theory explains that a firm must develop key human resource competencies and integrate the skills with latest technology and tools to enhance their performance in the workplace as well as contribute to the overall performance of the organization. Competency theory has however been criticized for assuming that competency translate to performance. The performance by employees is based on other factors that are critical like motivation and remuneration (Boyd, Whitehead, Thille, Ginsburg, Brydges, & Kuper, 2018). The theory is relevant on the association between competence of project staff and implementation of public

infrastructural projects. Competent staff in terms of skills, experience and training should lead to improved implementation in public infrastructure projects carried out by REREC.

2.2 Empirical Review

2.2.1 Environmental Regulations and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

An empirical study investigated the influence of environmental regulations on the Nairobi county construction projects. The research adopted correlational research design with the study targeting eight hundred and twenty-four construction firms that are registered in Nairobi County (Gichamba&Kithinji, 2019). The sample size of two hundred and sixty-nine was selected based on stratified sampling technique. Data was collected based on primary and secondary techniques of data collection with primary data collected through filling of questionnaires and secondary data collected from the records of the construction firms. The research revealed that waste management and water use regulations had a major impact on construction projects performance. Additionally, the study revealed that physical planning and noise regulations did not have significant effect on the performance of construction projects. A study in United Kingdom reported that the use of Section 60 of Noise Pollution Act of the year 1974 by authorities in the United Kingdom had increased significantly to curb noise pollutants emanating from construction of buildings. The local authorities' willingness to mitigate and control the associated negative impacts of noise pollution abatement notice under enforceability options of the EPA 1990 was also used to curb noise pollution (Pinsents& Masons, 2016). However, the noise controls in terms of associated cost had ballooned the cost of construction projects. Manvell and Stollery (2014) argued that new infrastructure construction causes significant noise pollution to the surrounding environment especially mega infrastructural projects in Canada. For instance, Diamond project in West Toronto in the state of Canada which resulted to noise pollution when they were constructing a massive underpass to separate commuter railway line from freight rails, which was at the center of the community. However, the project failed to address stakeholders' outcry, this forced the transport regulatory authority to intervene by specifying alternative, and advanced technological policies that could be used in the future to impose operation limits and reported cost increase that could extend project completion by three more years.

2.2.2 Construction Standards Regulation and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

A study in Nairobi Kenya evaluated the causal effect link between construction regulations and the performance of construction projects undertaken in Nairobi county Kenya. The study adopted causal study design to collect and analyze data (Ndumia, 2015). Simple random sampling was used to select the sample size comprising of various players in the construction industry including building contractors, quantity surveyors, and licensed architects. The study established that various regulations had significant effect on construction projects. Empirical analysis on occupational health and safety on construction sites examined the practice of health and safety management regulations during project implementation. In seeking to answer the research questions, the study adopted descriptive design where 30 construction sites in Nairobi County were selected through random sampling (Kibe, 2016). The study adopted questionnaires to collect both quantitative and qualitative data from site supervisors and workers on NCA registered construction sites and descriptive statistics used for data analysis. The study revealed that most of the accidents, injuries and other ailments at construction sites were due to accidental falling and injuries as well as health related issues associated with the work environment. According to the workers accidents and injuries mostly occur from failure to observe construction codes and operational health safety standards and had a high impact on construction progress. Another study on occupational health and safety in constructions works in Nairobi evaluated the compliance level with occupational health and safety standards in construction places within Nairobi County. The study adopted cross sectional research design with the study targeting eight hundred construction projects approved by the county government. The study adopted selected sixty construction sites from the target population based on multistage random sampling technique (Ogetii ,2019). The study delivered questionnaires, interviews and observation to collect data from various safety employees working in construction sites. The study revealed that majority of construction sites were registered with relevant authorities and that compliance level with the occupation health and safety standards was derailed by lack of advised knowledge on safety practices, exorbitant safety costs, negative impact on project schedule, and lack of commitment by management and lower productivity.

2.2.3 Financial Management Regulations and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

A study in Canada on implementation success of projects evaluated procurement legislation among three states in Canada with the intent of evaluating how they are integrated into the implementation of projects. The study adopted comparative research design study where the implementation of project was compared with how the procurement laws were integrated into the projected performance (Jobidon, Lemieux & Beauregard, 2018).The study revealed that transactional features of procurement process ought to be counter balanced and checked on the implementation of

integrated project implementation with emphasis on relational values. Empirical study in Nakuru Kenya examined the casual effect relationship between budgetary process and performance of construction and infrastructural projects done by Nakuru county government. The study specifically examined the influence of financial capacity of the county government on performance of the construction projects (Isaboke&Kwasira, 2016). Data analysis employed regression to examine the causal effect link between financial capacity of the county government and performance of the construction projects with the study establishing a major effect of financial capacity of the county government on the performance of construction projects undertaken by the county government. A study in Nyandarua county of Kenya evaluated the causal effect relationship between financial factors and performance of government projects. The study specifically examined the effect of budgetary controls, access to funding and financial training of the county staff on performance of the projects carried out by the county government (Mutheu&Muturi, 2018). A study in Nigeria by evaluated the relationship between implementation of large infrastructure projects and governance. The study adopted qualitative design relying on qualitative data. The research revealed that governance adopted in projects affected the projects both negatively and positively (Zarewa, Ibrahim, Ibrahim &Adogbo, 2018). The study revealed that governance features that positively affected projects included; setting aside of adequate financial resources, project risk management that is inclusive, simple and clear governance policies.

2.2.4 County Government Licensing and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

County governments are devolved government units given specific authority and responsibility according to the constitution of the concerned country. The devolution in Kenyan case is based on thematic matters relating to the operationalization of the constitutional provisions on devolved government as provided for in Chapter 11 of the 2010 Constitution of Kenya (GOK, 2010). County governments have the mandate to provide basic social economic infrastructure due the citizens living within the boundaries of the county. In Kenya case, the services offered by county governments include health and water, housing, basic education, garbage collection, urban public transport control, sewerage treatment, physical planning and development control and fire services among other services. Infrastructure developers must follow different counties' licensing requirements as detailed in their respective public finance policies. Nairobi City County passed and adopted a new "Financial Act of 2013" that became in operation in 2013. The Act refined and amended ways of evaluating building projects licensing fees as wells as consolidation of various costs for the approval of the concerned building projects. The permit fee is now based on size of the proposed building in terms of cost per square meter. The cost per square meter of the building changes with type of building whether for residential or commercial purposes. A construction project developer is required to get their architectural designs approved through the county government department of development by paying requisite fees. The project developer is required to submit requisite fees accompanied by land title deed, copy of architect's license and architectural drawings and plans of the proposed building (Nairobi City County Government, 2013).

The development department of the county government is required to forward the application to various departments including Roads department, physical Planning, fire department, Public Health, electricity authority and Water department. Each of the department is required to evaluate various sections of the proposed building with regards to matters concerning them and issue permits for the project (Nairobi City County Government, 2013). On the issue of building permit by the county government, project developer is required to submit structural designs separately. The county government of Nairobi has undergone a lot of transformation aimed at shortening the time for issuing various permits for construction projects. The number of days it takes to get approval for construction projects has been reduced significantly from the initial 50 days to an average of 30 days. However, the actual number of days for approval of construction projects varies depending on the diligence of the architect and the complexity of the proposed construction projects (Daily Nation, 2014). Most construction projects done in the county governments are affected by long approval process that leads to skyrocketing of construction cost and time delays to project completion. The approval process by county government authorities has been faced with huddles including long approvals processes and lack of a single approval process (Productivity Commission, 2005). The developers are required to obtain different approvals from multiple agencies in relation to separate regulations governing building safety, public health, land use, environmental regulations among other regulations (Testa, Iraldo, & Frey, 2015).

2.3.5 Competence of Project Team and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

A study on SGR project evaluated the determinants of effective large projects implementation in Kenya. The study adopted descriptive survey design where the target population was one thousand, six hundred and forty four project experts involved in the construction of SGR infrastructure project (Mbiti, 2017). The study adopted OLS regression model to examine the association between project team competency, top management support, building information modelling technology, stakeholder participation and implementation of SGR from Mombasa to Nairobi. The study established that that project team competency, top management support, building information modelling technology

and stakeholder participation had major impact on implementation effectiveness of SGR project. A study in Kenya in the gated communities in Nairobi by examined the determinants of implementation of construction projects. The study collected and analyzed quantitative and qualitative data using a descriptive survey design where questionnaires were used for actual data collection (Kihoro&Waiganjo, 2015). The analysis of the data proceeded after data collection with regression analysis adopted to examine the causal effect relationship among project team competency, project planning, stakeholder management and proxies of project performance.

The study established that the causal link between project team competency, project planning, stakeholder management and project performance proxies was major. A study in Kuwait examined the impact of the skills of project managers on performance of complex construction projects. The study relied on critical literature analysis tools where extensive literature reviews was done on the association between skills of project managers carried and performance of complex construction projects (Alshammari1, Yahya, &Haron, 2020). The study revealed that effective implementation of complex construction projects were contingent on effective communication skills, effective planning, teamwork, effective resource management and risk management. A study in Pakistan evaluated the causal effect link obtaining among competence of project management, project complexities and performance of large of public sector projects. The independent variables were competence of project management and project complexities (Malik, 2019). The study revealed that project management competence had a major direct impact on project performance while project complexity had an inverse association with project performance. The two variables are jointly explained and their effect on the performance of mega engineering projects in Pakistan.”

III. METHODOLOGY.

3.1 Research Design, Population and Sampling

The research was descriptive research design. In this design no form of manipulation of variables is done. Participants were therefore be asked to provide their opinions regarding the magnitude of the association among study variables. The design enabled the researcher to examine the causal effect association among environmental regulations, building codes and standards regulations, financial regulations, county governments licensing, project staff commitment and implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The study targeted 481 permanent employees of REREC (REREC, 2020). The respondents comprised of employees from different departments including Supply Chain Management, Strategy and Planning, Legal Services, Renewable Energy, Finance, and Accounts, Business Development, Human Resources, Advocacy, Public Education & Awareness, Information Communication Technology, Corporate Communications, Process Audit, Research, Monitoring and Evaluation and Alternative Energy. The study focused on all types of electrification projects already undertaken and those still in progress at REREC. The projects included connecting schools, local markets, and community centers to electricity in the rural areas. The study opted for the formula by Kothari (2012) to determine the sample size to participate in the study. The formula is represented in the equation below:

$$\text{Thus, } n = \frac{z^2pqN}{(e^2(N-1) + z^2pq)}$$

Where e is the error for this study, taken as 7%; p is the population reliability, taken as p=0.5; q= (1-p), z is the normal distribution at 0.05 level of significance such that z =1.96, N is target population and n is sample size. The sample size was therefore calculated as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{(1.96*1.96*0.5*0.5*481)}{(0.07*0.07(481-1) + 1.96*1.96*0.5*0.5)} \\ n &= 139.6 \\ n &= 140 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in this study, the desired sample size given the target population of 481 permanent employees at REREC Headquarters was 140 respondents. The study used stratified random sampling method based on functional areas of management. The functional areas formed the strata for data collection. The sample size was distributed based on proportion of the number of items in each strata. Thereafter, specific staff to take part in the study were picked from the number of employees in each stratum.

3.2 Research Instruments and Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered to employees of REREC headquarters in Nairobi. The study adopted structured questionnaires that were Likert in nature. Likert Scale type questions enables the researcher to measure the level of

agreement or support of various statements by the respondents. The questionnaire were divided into various sections with questions meant to be used to collect data on demographic and specific objectives. In this study, 14 questionnaires were administered during the pre-test to 14 employees from National Oil Corporation of Kenya, Nairobi. National Oil was chosen as the Pilot Study given that National Oil Corporation and REREC are firm in energy sector hence employees share experience on how government regulations affects implementation of infrastructure projects subjects. Additionally, the National oil head office is also based in Nairobi hence the geographical similarity in the context of implementation of public infrastructure projects in the energy sector.

The information collected during the pilot study was used for the purpose of determination of the reliability and validity of the research instruments adopted in the study. The researcher involved various experts of project management to help in evaluating the content and face validity. The study adopted internal consistency measure tested based on Cronbach's Alpha. To ensure reliability, a predetermined threshold of 0.7 and above is needed in the Cronbach's Alpha (Mugenda&Mugenda, 2009). The researcher settled on reliability of above 0.75 to ensure that the questionnaires are reliable beyond any doubt. The researcher got appointment from the University Panel and REREC at different times to explain the purpose of the study. The researcher then printed the questionnaires. Each questionnaire was delivered to the selected respondents for filling." The questionnaires were distributed to the staff with the help of three research assistants. The research assistants were trained and were able to assist the respondents on how to fill the various sections of the questionnaires. The respondents had adequate time to fill the questionnaires. The researcher allowed the respondents one week to fill the questionnaires before their final collection for further analysis.

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques

Filled questionnaires were checked for completeness and adequacy for further analysis. The researcher then coded the questionnaires before the responses were entered into SPSS version 23. Data Analysis proceeded using descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics used included measures of central tendency and dispersal. The descriptive analysis involved frequency distribution, percentages, mean and standard deviation. The inferential analysis involved Pearson correlation coefficient and OLS regression." The Pearson correlation coefficient were bivariate in nature where each independent variable will be correlated with dependent variable to generate the correlation coefficient between them. A correlation coefficient between 0.1- 0.3 was considered weak, a correlation coefficient between 0.4-0.6 was considered moderate. A correlation coefficient between 0.7-0.9 was considered strong. Correlation of 0 means there is no correlation and correlation of 1 means perfect correlation. The ordinary least squares regression (OLS) output included the model summary, the ANOVA and regression coefficients. The regression enabled the study to establish the influence of selected government regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. Simple regression was applied with the dependent variable being regressed against each explanatory variable at a time. The regression model to be adopted to test the influence of selected government regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC is presented in equation (1).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + e \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Where Y = implementation of public infrastructure projects (dependent variable), B_0 = is the intercept term, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = are the coefficients of the explanatory variables, X_1 = Environmental regulation, X_2 = Construction standards and codes regulation, X_3 = Public financial management regulation, X_4 = County government licensing regulation, X_5 = Competence of project team, e = Error term

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Response Rate

Out of the 140 questionnaires issued, 112 were returned adequately filled. This generated a response rate of 80%. The response was adequate for further analysis as it was above the threshold of 70% as suggested by Mugenda and Mugenda (2009).The researcher with the help of trained research assistants made sure they followed up with all respondents who were issued with questionnaires. The researcher also assured the top management and respondents that information collected was for academic purposes only.

4.2 Demographic Information

The study established that 57(50.89%) of the respondents were males while 55(49.10%) were females. This implies that the females were well matched against males in the organization. Regarding the length of stay at REREC, the study

established that 67(59.82%) of the respondents had worked at the firm for between 3-6 years. This was followed by 28(25%) who had been attached at the firm for over 6 years. The remaining 17(15.17%) had worked in the firm for two years and below. The study therefore concludes that the staff had adequate experience in their duties given that 95(84.82%) of the staff had experience three years and above. Finally, the study examined the educational attainment by the respondents. The study revealed that those holding bachelors and diploma qualification were 35(31.25%) and 40 (35.71%) respectively. Those holding certificate qualification were 23(20.5%) while those holding post graduate degree were 14(12.5%). The finding has revealed that 98(87.5%) of the staff had at least a diploma qualification in their fields of work hence it can be concluded that the staff possessed adequate professional training to enable them perform their duties in various areas to enable REREC to achieve its goals and mandate.

4.3 Descriptive Statistics of the Study Variables

The study sought to examine the variables of the study using descriptive statistics. The study adopted mean and standard deviation. The descriptive analysis has been presented according to study variables as shown in succeeding subsections. The respondents were required to rate a number of statements regarding government regulations based on five point scale where 5 was strongly agree, 4 was agree, 3 was neutral, 2 was disagree and 1 was strongly disagree. The findings are presented in table 1-6.

Table 1: Perception on Environmental Regulations

Statements on Environmental Regulations	Mean	SD
Disposal of wastes as required in the waste management regulation is very expensive	4.4107	.57819
Noise pollution licenses contributes to the cost of REREC's projects in a significant way	4.3661	.61506
The environmental impact assessment are very costly to REREC.	4.3571	.59815
The cost of mitigating various environmental impact adds to the cost of REREC projects in a significant way.	4.3571	.69564
Measurement and procedures for noise and vibrations reduction as adds to the costs of projects in a significant way	4.2857	.67688
Environmental impact assessment is usually carried out before we can undertake any project.	4.2857	.63570
Waste management regulation are critical on how you dispose construction wastes emanating from REREC's projects	4.2589	.65410
Water regulations affects the cost of water used for projects being undertaken by REREC contractors in a significant way	4.1875	.52900
You aware of various environmental regulations that are affecting project implementation at REREC.	4.0625	.52473
Overall Mean score	4.2857	.61193

The statements in Table 1 have been organized in descending order based on mean. The statement that was highly ranked based on mean was "disposal of wastes as required in the waste management regulation is very expensive." The statement had mean responses tending towards strongly agree (M=4.4107) with standard deviation distributed away from the mean with 0.57 units implying that the organization is required by law to properly dispose all its wastes that are generated in construction works which is an expensive affair and adds to cost of the projects. The statement with the lowest mean response rate was "you are aware of various environmental regulations that are affecting project implementation at REREC" as evidenced by mean responses and standard deviation tending to agree (M= 4.0625 and SD=.52473). The overall mean on all statements was 4.2857 implying that the respondents tended to agree with statements about environmental regulations and how they influence implementation of public infrastructural projects implemented by REREC.

Table 2: Perception Statement on Construction Codes and Standards Regulations

Statement on Construction Codes and Standards Regulations	Mean	SD
Compliance to NCA construction and building guidelines have led to improved performance and quality of projects undertaken by REREC	4.4196	.59485
The compliance to health and safety standards have led to reduced injuries at work, reduced sickness and reduced compensation costs	4.3750	.58702
Staff and Contractors involved in projects regularly undergoes training programs organized by NCA	4.3214	.63266
The construction controls stated in the NCA construction and building regulations are very costly and leads to cost outstripping	4.3125	.58558
Our organization has Health and Safety measures in place when carrying out projects	4.3036	.56695
The construction techniques & materials used in REREC projects have been standardized to enhance quality	4.2946	.62440
National Construction Authority regularly visits your work sites to enforce the code of conduct for REREC contractors.	4.2857	.60670
The costs of projects undertaken by REREC have gone up because of adoption of construction and building guidelines issued by NCA	4.0804	.46766
Overall Mean Score	4.2991	.5832

The statements in table 2 have been organized in descending order based on mean score per statement. The statements that was highly supported was compliance to NCA construction and building guidelines have led to improved performance and quality of projects undertaken by REREC . The mean response and standard deviation on the statement tended to strong agreement (M= 4.4196 and SD=.5948) implying that strict adherence to NCA construction and building guidelines has been helpful in improving the quality of projects carried out by REREC. The statement with lowest rank was costs of projects undertaken by REREC have gone up because of adoption of construction and building guidelines issued by NCA as shown by mean response and standard deviation nearing agreement (M= 4.0804 and SD= .46766). The response implies that adherence to construction codes and standards had cost implication for REREC. The overall mean score was 4.2991 implying that the responds were of general opinion that the building codes and construction standards are significant to implementation of public infrastructure projects implemented by REREC.

Table 3: Perceptions on Public Financial Management Regulations

Statements on Public Financial Management Regulations	Mean	SD
The management performs budgetary controls on all undergoing projects to ensure they are within the set budget	4.5357	.65662
REREC usually seeks external funding from donors to supplement the resources given by the Treasury	4.4554	.69604
Each project in REREC is allocated adequate financial resources from the conception to implementation stage	4.3661	.73516
REREC awards the tenders to the lowest bidders in every tender process.	4.2321	.60003
The top management prepares budgets before undertaking any infrastructure project	4.2143	.50988
Suppliers of REREC are always pre-qualified and entered into the database.	4.1786	.70025
The financial allocation by the Treasury is adequate to enable REREC carry out planned projects.	3.9643	.42296
Overall Mean Score	4.2780	.61727

The statements in table 3 have been ordered in descending order based on mean. The statement that was ranked the highest was that the management of REREC performs budgetary controls on all undergoing projects to ensure they are within the set budget. This was depicted by mean response nearing strong agreement (M=4.5357) and standard deviation slightly distributed with 0.65662 units around the mean. The response implies that all projects being undertaken at REREC must be based on budgetary controls as expected by Controller of Budgets and Auditor General.

The statement that was least supported was that the financial allocation by the Treasury is adequate to enable REREC carry out planned projects as depicted by mean response tending to neutral (M= 3.9643) and slight standard deviation of .42296 units around the mean. The response implies that the budget allocated for projects by the exchequer is never adequate and sometimes REREC has to seek donor funds and PPPs to supplement money from government. The overall mean score was 4.2780 meaning that in general, the respondents were in agreement that REREC follows the Public Financial Management Regulations and that the regulation is impacting on implementation of public infrastructure projects implemented by REREC.

Table 4: Perception on County Government Licensing Regulations

Statements on County Government Licensing Regulations	Mean	SD
The county governments visits sites and penalizes errand developers	4.500	.5851
All County Governments have not formulated a statutory and regulatory framework to embrace digital system for management of developments applications	4.500	.6296
The county governments licensing department issues construction permits very late	4.410	.6085
REREC must obtain approval from the county government before undertaking any projects	4.383	.6331
The process of obtaining approvals from the county governments are long	4.366	.6436
There are numerous approvals to be obtained from various approval authorities before we can undertake any project	4.348	.6108
The county government charges heavily for failure to acquire any approval	4.223	.6254
The cost of obtaining licenses and approvals from the county government is so high	3.928	.4183
Overall Mean Score	4.332	0.5943

The statements in table 4 have been ordered from the most supported to the least supported based on mean response. The statement that was ranked the highest based on mean was that the county governments visits sites and penalizes errand developers to increase compliance as depicted by mean response tending towards strong agreement slight standard deviation of .58 units around the mean. The response implies that the county government is very strict on penalizing errand developers to improved compliance with County Government Licensing Regulations. The statement that was ranked the lowest based on mean response was that the cost of obtaining licenses and approvals from the county government is as high as depicted by mean and standard deviation tending towards agreement(M=3.928 and SD =.4183). The response implies that the responses agreed that the cost of obtaining licenses and approvals from the county government is so high. The overall mean score was 4.332 implying that the respondents were of the general opinion that County Government Licensing Regulations is affecting the success of the implementation of public infrastructure projects.

Table 5: Perception on Competence of Project Team

Statements on Competence of Project Team	Mean	SD
The staff at our organization are highly experienced in their areas	4.366	.6575
There is a good mix of experiences and competence among staff members	4.267	.7226
The organization has the right leaders at every department of the organization	4.241	.7855
The organization usually organizes in-house training for staff	4.232	.7471
The staff at our organization possess the required educational backgrounds	4.214	.6900
The staff have the right attitude to perform their duties	4.035	.6140
Overall Mean Score	4.225	.7027

The statements in table 5 were ranked based on mean responses in a descending order. The highest ranked statements about competence of project staff was that the staff at REREC are highly experienced in their areas of expertise. This was evidenced by mean response tending to strong agreement and slightly small standard deviation from the mean (M= 4.366 and SD= .6575). This implies that generally, the staff working at REREC are highly experienced and should enable them perform their duties of project implementation. The lowest ranked statement was that the staff have the right attitude to perform their duties as shown by mean response (M=4.035) tending to agreement and standard deviation of SD= 0.6140 around the mean. The findings implies that staff attitude was critical for project implementation and that the staff at REREC were generally of good attitude required to perform their work with diligence. The overall mean score

was 4.225 which is tending to strong agreement hence it can be concluded that the staff attached to REREC have got the right competence needed to perform their duty of implementing public infrastructural projects.

4.4 Regression Analysis

4.4.1 Environmental Regulation and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

The study examined the influence environmental regulation on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The study adopted simple OLS regression model to examine the influence of environmental regulation on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The regression output included the model summary, analysis of variances (ANOVA) and regression coefficients. The findings are presented in table 7.

Table 7: Environmental Regulations and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.347 ^a	.120	.112	.31604		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.503	1	1.503	15.046	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.987	110	.100		
	Total	12.490	111			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.590	.435		5.948	.000
	Environmental Regulation	-0.393	.101	.347	-3.879	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Environmental Regulation

The model summary in table 7 shows that environmental regulation explains 12% of the variation in implementation of public infrastructure projects as depicted by coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .120$). The ANOVA revealed that environmental regulation had a significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($f = 15.046$, $p = .000 < .05$). In addition, the regression coefficient revealed a significant negative influence of environmental regulation on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($\beta_1 = -.393$, $t = -3.879$, $p = .000 < .05$). The study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that environmental regulations have no significant influence on the implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC.

4.4.2 Construction Standards and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

The study examined the influence building codes and construction standards on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The regression output is presented in table 8.

Table 8: Construction Standards and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.471 ^a	.222	.215	.29719		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.774	1	2.774	31.410	.000 ^b
	Residual	9.716	110	.088		
	Total	12.490	111			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.847	.434		4.255	.000
	Construction codes and standards regulations	.565	.101	.471	5.604	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Construction codes and standards regulations

The model summary in table 8 shows that construction standards explains 22.2% of the variation in implementation of public infrastructure projects as depicted by coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .222$). The ANOVA revealed that construction standards and codes had a significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($f = 31.41$, $p = .000 < .05$). In addition, the regression coefficient revealed a significant positive influence of construction standards on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($\beta_2 = .565$, $t = 5.604$, $p = .000 < .05$). The study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that construction standards and codes have no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC.

4.4.3 Public Financial Management Regulation and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

The study evaluated the influence public financial management regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The regression output is presented in table 9.

Table 9: Public Financial Management Regulations and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.445 ^a	.198	.191	.30168		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.479	1	2.479	27.234	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.011	110	.091		
	Total	12.490	111			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.567	.329		7.811	.000
	Public Financial management regulations	.399	.077	.445	5.219	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implimnetation of PIP

b. Predictors: (Constant), Public Financial management Regulations

The model summary in table 4.9 shows that public financial management regulations explains 19.8% of the variation in implementation of public infrastructure projects as depicted by coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .198$). The ANOVA showed that public financial management regulations had a significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($f = 27.234, p = .000 < .05$). In addition, the regression coefficient revealed a significant positive influence of public financial management regulations on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($\beta_3 = .399, t = 5.219, p = .000 < .05$). The research rejected the null hypothesis that Public financial management regulations have no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC.

4.4.4 County Government Licensing and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

The study analyzed the influence county government licensing on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The regression output included the model summary, analysis of variances (ANOVA) and regression coefficients. The findings are presented in table 10.

Table 10: County Government Licensing and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.533 ^a	.284	.278	.28508		
ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.550	1	3.550	43.684	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.940	110	.081		
	Total	12.490	111			
Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	B	Std. Error	Beta		
	County Government Lisensing	2.015	.343		5.875	.000
		-.522	.079	.533	-6.609	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), County Government Lisensing

The model summary in table 4.10 shows that county government licensing explains 28.4% of the variation in implementation of public infrastructure projects as depicted by coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .284$). The ANOVA showed that county government licensing had a significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($f = 43.684, p = .000 < .05$). In addition, the regression coefficient revealed a significant negative influence of county government licensing on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($\beta_4 = -.522, t = -6.609, p = .000 < .05$). The study therefore rejected null hypothesis that county government licensing has no significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC.

4.4.5 Competence of Project Team and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

The study finally evaluated the influence competence of project team on implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC. The study adopted simple OLS regression model to examine the influence of competence of project team on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The regression output included the model summary, analysis of variances (ANOVA) and regression coefficients. The findings are presented in table 11.

Table 11: Competence of Project Team and Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.606 ^a	.367	.361	.26814		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.581	1	4.581	63.715	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.909	110	.072		
	Total	12.490	111			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	2.466	.228		10.810	.000
	Competence of project team	.428	.054	.606	7.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects

b. Predictors: (Constant), Competence of project team

The model summary in table 4.11 shows that competence of project team explains 36.7% of the variation in implementation of public infrastructure projects as depicted by coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .367$). The ANOVA showed that competence of project team had a significant influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($f = 63.715$, $p = .000 < .05$). In addition, the regression coefficient revealed a significant positive influence of competence of project team on implementation of public infrastructure projects ($\beta_3 = .428$, $t = 7.982$, $p = .000 < .05$). The research therefore concluded that competence of project team moderates the relationship between selected government regulations and implementation of public infrastructure projects by REREC.

V. CONCLUSION

Regarding the first objective, the study concluded that Environmental regulations had a significant negative influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The negative influence implies that when the number of environmental regulations increases, the cost of complying with these regulations increases the project budget and implementation of public infrastructure projects is affected negatively as less projects are planned for. In relation to the second objective, the study concluded that construction standards and codes had a significant positive influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The positive relationship means that enhancement of the building regulation by updating the building construction codes leads to better quality projects thereby improved public infrastructure project implementation. The research concluded that public financial management regulations had a significant positive influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The positive influence implies that strict adherence to the public financial management regulations is associated with improvement in the discipline of management of project funds and leads to value for money. Concerning the fourth objective, the study concluded that county government licensing had a significant negative influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The negative influence implies that the number of county government licensing required and the complexity of the process of getting the licence impacts implementation of public infrastructure projects negatively. In reference to the fifth objective, the study concluded that competence of project team had a significant positive influence on implementation of public infrastructure projects. The positive influence of competence of project team on implementation of public infrastructure projects implies that when the staff competence improves in terms of skills, experience and attitude, the implementation of public infrastructure projects improves further. The study therefore rejected all the null hypotheses.

Based on the findings the study, the research makes several recommendations. First, regarding Environmental regulation, the study recommends to management of REREC to be vigilant and ensure observance of existing environmental regulations in Kenya. The corporation should ensure that they do not contravene the environmental regulation leading to fines and other legal liability arising in the process. The legal liability leads to increased cost of doing projects and further affecting project implementation negatively through over blown budgets. The government should also check on environmental regulations which retard implementation of public infrastructure projects and amend them where necessary. Secondly, the study recommends that REREC in partnership with NCA and other industry players should explore, find and adopt more new construction technologies and standards recommended in the construction codes and standards book. New technologies come with superior environmental characteristics and energy saving materials that cost less, are more efficient and lead to resource savings which will be used for additional infrastructure projects.

Thirdly, the study suggests that the management at the REREC continues to adhere to the Public Financial Management Act and the Public Procurement and Assets Disposal Act. The two acts are critical in transparent management of funds meant for various public infrastructure projects. The study also makes recommendation regarding county government licensing. Given that, different counties have different licensing requirements, the study recommends that the county government should adopt standard procedures. The number of days required to get various permits regarding public infrastructure projects should be reduced significantly through adoption of technology. The senate that is in charge of devolution should encourage county governments to adopt standard procedures regarding licensing of public infrastructure projects. This should include creation of one stop shops where all the licensing should be centralized. Finally, regarding competence of project team, the study recommends to the management of REREC should continue recruiting highly qualified employees for its vacant positions. Additionally, the management should put in place on job training opportunities aimed at updating the skills of staff regarding new working methods they may have not been trained to handle while in the tertiary colleges. The management should also work on employees attitude and employee reward. This ensures staff deliver as per mandate.

REFERENCES

- [1.] AbdWahab, M. R. (2016). The performance measures of supply chain management for infrastructure project (Doctoral dissertation, UniversitiTeknologi MARA).
- [2.] Alaimo, L. S., &Maggino, F. (2020). Sustainable development goals indicators at territorial level: Conceptual and methodological issues – The Italian perspective. *Social Indicators Research*, 147(2), 383-419.
- [3.] Alshammari, F., Yahya, K., &Haron, Z. B. (2020, January). Project Manager's Skills for improving the performance of complex projects in Kuwait Construction Industry: A Review. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 713, No. 1, p. 012041). IOP Publishing.
- [4.] Ametepey, S. O., Ansah, S. K., & Edu-Buandoh, K. B. M. (2015). Assessing factors affecting implementation of the national building regulations (LI 1630) in Ghana. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 5(2), 66-73.
- [5.] Ametepey, O., Aigbavboa, C., &Ansah, K. (2015). Barriers to successful implementation of sustainable construction in the Ghanaian construction industry. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 3, 1682-1689.
- [6.] Assbeihat, J. M. (2016). Factors affecting delays on private construction projects. *Technology*, 7(2), 22-33.
- [7.] AyebeBotchway, E., &Yeboah-Boateng, E. O. (2019). IoT Readiness of Project Management Teams Within Local Government Organizations in Ghana. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 10(07).
- [8.] Becker, G. (1986). The public interest hypothesis revisited: A new test of Peltzman's theory of regulation. *Public choice*, 49(3), 223-234.
- [9.] Beckrich, A. (2018). The Top 5 Environmental Stories of 2017. *The Science Teacher*, 85(1), 8-8.
- [10.] Bartle, P. (2008). The Human Factor and Community Empowerment. *Review of human factor studies*, 14(1).
- [11.] Boyd, V. A., Whitehead, C. R., Thille, P., Ginsburg, S., Brydges, R., &Kuper, A. (2018). Competency-based medical education: the discourse of infallibility. *Medical education*, 52(1), 45-57.
- [12.] Bozeman, B., &Straussman, J. D. (1982). Shrinking budgets and the shrinkage of budget theory. *Public Administration Review*, 42(6), 509-515.
- [13.] Christudason, A. (2018). Termination Legislation: Property Rights or Wrongs?. In *Multi-Owned Property in the Asia-Pacific Region* (pp. 39-63). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- [14.] Cunningham, J. A., O'reilly, P., Dolan, B., O'kane, C., &Mangematin, V. (2016). Publicly funded principal investigators allocation of time for public sector entrepreneurship activities. *Economia e PoliticaIndustriale*, 43(4), 383-408.

- [15.] Damoah, I. S., Ayakwah, A., Aryee, K. J., & Twum, P. (2020). The rise of PPPs in public sector affordable housing project implementation in Ghana: challenges and policy direction. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 1-14.
- [16.] Dosumu, O. S. (2018). Perceived effects of prevalent errors in contract documents on construction projects. *Construction Economics and Building*, 18(1), 1-26.
- [17.] Elhami, S., Ban, M., Mousaviasl, S., & Zahedi, A. (2018). Self-Evaluation of Nurses Clinical Competency based on Benner Theory. *World Family Medicine Journal: Incorporating the Middle East Journal of Family Medicine*, 99(5897), 1-7.
- [18.] Enshassi, A., Kochendoerfer, B., & Al Ghoul, H. (2016). Factors affecting sustainable performance of construction projects during project life cycle phases. *Factors Affecting Sustainable Performance of Construction Projects during Project Life Cycle Phases*, 7(1).
- [19.] Erastus, K. K., & Wuchuan, P. (2017). Flaws in the Current Building Code and Code Making Process in Kenya. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 6(5), 24-30.
- [20.] Erebor, E., Ibem, E. O., & Adewale, B. A. (2019). Current research trends on sustainable construction project delivery. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and*, 1-19.
- [21.] Gichamba, S., & Kithinji, C. (2019). Influence of environmental regulations in the performance of construction projects in Nairobi County, Kenya. *International Academic Journal of Information Sciences and Project Management*, 3(4), 184-209.
- [22.] Hodge, G. A., & Greve, C. (2017). On public-private partnership performance: A contemporary review. *Public Works Management & Policy*, 22(1), 55-78.
- [23.] Ihuah, P. W., & Benebo, A. M. (2017). An assessment of the causes and effects of abandonment of development projects on real property values in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Applied, Natural and social sciences*, 2(5), 25-36.
- [24.] Ika, L. A. (2016). Project management for development in Africa: Why projects are failing and what can be done about it. *Project management journal*, 43(4), 27-41.
- [25.] Isaboke, M. E., & Kwasira, J. (2016). Assessment of Budgeting Process on Financial Performance of County Government of Nakuru Kenya. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 4(5), 134-150.
- [26.] Jiménez, A., Jiang, G. F., Petersen, B., & Gammelgaard, J. (2019). Within-country religious diversity and the performance of private participation infrastructure projects. *Journal of Business Research*, 95, 13-25.
- [27.] Jobidon, G., Lemieux, P., & Beaugard, R. (2018). Implementation of integrated project implementation in Québec's procurement for public infrastructure: a comparative and relational perspective. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2648.
- [28.] Johnston, J. (2017). The public interest: A new way of thinking for public relations?. *Public Relations Inquiry*, 6(1), 5-22.
- [29.] Kibe, K. N. (2016). Assessment of health and safety management on construction sites in Kenya: a case of construction projects in Nairobi County. Nairobi: Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.
- [30.] Kihoro, M. W., & Waiganjo, E. (2015). Factors affecting performance of projects in the construction industry in Kenya: A survey of gated communities in Nairobi County. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 2(2), 37-66.
- [31.] Kimani, M., & Musungu, T. (2010). Reforming and Restructuring the Planning and Building Laws and Regulations in Kenya for Sustainable Development. In Unpublished paper presented at the 46th ISOCaRP Congress. Nairobi, Kenya.
- [32.] Kimani, E. M., & Ojwang, B. O. (2016). Influence of Budgetary Controls on Service Implementation in County Government of Nakuru in Kenya.
- [33.] Kioko, J. M. (2016). Causes of building failures in Africa: A case study on collapsing structures in Kenya. *IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE)*, 2278-1684.
- [34.] Kraak, M. J., Ricker, B., & Engelhardt, Y. (2018). Challenges of mapping Sustainable Development Goals indicators data. *ISPRS international journal of geo-information*, 7(12), 482.
- [35.] Lamka, A. H., Masu, S. M., Wanyona, G., Dianga, S., & Gwaya, A. O. (2017). Factors influencing effective productivity on construction sites in Nairobi County. *International journal of soft Computing and Engineering (IJSJCE)*, 4(5), 24-30.
- [36.] Lindrianasari, L., Kufepaksi, M., Asmaranti, Y., & Komalasari, A. (2018). Social and Environmental Responsibility in Developing Countries: A Theoretical Approach to Regulation. *International Journal of GEOMATE*, 15(49), 47-52.

- [37.] Malik, S., Fatima, F., Imran, A., Chuah, L. F., Klemeš, J. J., Khaliq, I. H., & Akbar, M. M. (2019). Improved project control for sustainable development of construction sector to reduce environment risks. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 240, 118214.
- [38.] Mana'an, O. A., Ahadzie, D. K., Panford, J. K., & Proverbs, D. G. (2016). Competency-based evaluation of project managers' performance in mass house building projects in Ghana—the fuzzy set theory approach. *Journal of Science and Technology (Ghana)*, 34(1), 46-62.
- [39.] Manvell, D., & Stollery, P. (2014, October). New techniques to determine specific noise for increasing the effectiveness of continuous unattended noise monitoring systems. In *INTER-NOISE and NOISE-CON Congress and Conference Proceedings (Vol. 249, No. 4, pp. 3642-3649)*. Institute of Noise Control Engineering.
- [40.] Marleno, R., Surjono, S., Wateno, O., Muhammad, I. S., & Dahlan, A. (2018, November). The Influence of Stakeholder Factors Affecting the Success of Construction Projects In Indonesia. In *IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics (pp. 1-10)*.
- [41.] Mbiti, C. K. (2017). Factors influencing effective implementation of mega projects in Kenya: A case of The Standard Gauge Railway Project. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 3(5), 981-998.
- [42.] Mizutani, F., & Nakamura, E. (2019). Regulation, public interest, and private interest: an empirical investigation of firms in Japan. *Empirical Economics*, 56(4), 1433-1454
- [43.] Muraraneza, C., & Mtshali, G. N. (2018). Conceptualization of competency based curricula in pre-nursing and midwifery education: A grounded theory approach. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 28, 175-181.
- [44.] Neuby, B. L. (1997). On the lack of a budget theory. *Public Administration Quarterly*, 131-142.
- [45.] Ndumia, S. N. (2015). Influence of regulatory framework on performance of building construction projects in Nairobi County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- [46.] Niazi, G. A., & Painting, N. (2017, September). Critical success factors for public private partnership in the Afghanistan construction industry. In *International Conference on Engineering, Project, and Product Management (pp. 91-98)*. Springer, Cham.
- [47.] Nyaga, K. G. (2014). Role of project management skills on performance of construction projects: a case of selected construction firms in Mombasa County, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- [48.] Nyamweya, J. M., & Obuya, M. O. (2020). Role of Financial Efficiency and Income Distribution on the Relationship between Economic Growth on Poverty Levels in East Africa Community Countries. *International Journal of Finance and Banking Research*, 6(4), 65-73.
- [49.] Obuya, M. O., & Olweny, T. (2017). Effect of bank's lending behaviour on loan losses of listed commercial banks in Kenya. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 5(1), 135-144
- [50.] Ogetii, J. B. (2019). An Assessment of Occupational Health and Safety Practices at Construction Sites in Nairobi City Region, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, university of nairobi).
- [51.] Oguntona, O. A., & Aigbavboa, C. O. (2019). Barriers hindering biomimicry adoption and application in the construction industry. *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 11(3), 289-297.
- [52.] Onyango, L. B., Bwisa, H., & Orwa, G. (2017). Critical Factors Influencing the Implementation of Public Infrastructure Projects in Kenya: A Case of Thika Sub-County, Kiambu County Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 7(5), 2250-3153.
- [53.] Owiti, J. (2019). Evaluating the Effectiveness of the Waste Management Regulation, Legal Notice 121, 2006, in Relation to Solid Waste Management in Kiambu Town, Kenya (Doctoral dissertation, university of nairobi).
- [54.] Parsa, A. G., & Farshchi, M. A. (2016). Environmental regulations and the real estate industry. *Property Management*.
- [55.] Penyalver, D., Turró, M., & Williamson, J. B. (2019). Measuring the value for money of transport infrastructure procurement; an intergenerational approach. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 119, 238-254.
- [56.] Pinsent Masons. (2016). Connected and autonomous Vehicles: The emerging legal challenges. Retrieved from <https://www.pinsentmasons.com/en/media/publications/connected-andautonomous-vehicles-the-emerging-legal-challenges/>
- [57.] Rhyner, C. R., Schwartz, L. J., Wenger, R. B., & Kohrell, M. G. (2017). *Waste management and resource recovery*. CRC Press.
- [58.] Roth, W. M., & von Unger, H. (2018, September). Current perspectives on research ethics in qualitative research. In *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research (Vol. 19, No. 3)*.
- [59.] Sammy, P. M., & Muturi, W. (2008). Project Specific Factors Affecting Performance Of County Government Projects In Kenya: A Case Of Nyandarua County.
- [60.] Sánchez-Silva, M. (2019). Managing infrastructure systems through changeability. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 25(1), 04018040.

- [61.] Santin, O. G., Itard, L., &Visscher, H. (2019). The effect of occupancy and building characteristics on energy use for space and water heating in Dutch residential stock. *Energy and buildings*, 41(11), 1223-1232.
- [62.] Sarhan, J., Xia, B., Fawzia, S., Karim, A., &Olanipekun, A. (2018). Barriers to implementing lean construction practices in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) construction industry. *Construction Innovation*.
- [63.] Shair, U. I. (2016). Influence of Project Management Skills of Staff on Performance of Government Funded Projects in Kenya: The case of Kazi Kwa Vijana Initiative in Kibera, Nairobi County. Unpublished Masters of Arts in Project Planning and Management Thesis: University of Nairobi.
- [64.] Sun, W., Bocchini, P., & Davison, B. D. (2020). Resilience metrics and measurement methods for transportation infrastructure: the state of the art. *Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure*, 5(3), 168-199.
- [65.] Testa, F., Iraldo, F., & Frey, M. (2015). The effect of environmental regulation on firms' competitive performance: The case of the building & construction sector in some EU regions. *Journal of environmental management*, 92(9), 2136-2144.
- [66.] Zarewa, G. A., Ibrahim, A. D., Ibrahim, Y. M., &Adogbo, K. J. (2018). Governance Impact Assessment on Large Infrastructure Project (LIP) Delivery. *Journal of Engineering, Project & Production Management*, 8(1)